

Studies in the Cyclooctane Series: Part IV. The Condensation of Ethyl Cyclooctan-1-one-2-carboxylate with Arylamines and the Synthesis of 2:3-hexamethylene-aryl Substituted-4-Quinolones

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Ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-carboxylate is condensed with various primary arylamines in presence of glacial acetic acid at room temperature to furnish ethyl 1-arylamino-cyclooct-1-one-2-carboxylates; these are subsequently cyclised by heating at 240–250° to yield the respective 2:3-hexamethylene-aryl-substituted-4-quinolones.

β -keto esters react with primary arylamines to yield a number of products depending upon the concentration of the reactants and the reaction temperature, the latter being more important in controlling the nature of the products formed. These arise because of the presence of the carbonyl and ester groups which are the two active centres in the molecule of the ester.

Thus, ethylacetoacetate on condensation with aniline and other primary amines gives a number of products¹⁻⁷. Jadhav⁸ referring to the work of Knorr¹ describes that the condensation product of the above β -ketoester with aniline had the structure (I) which is hardly correct since Knorr never suggested this structure.

The amount of work done on the condensation of cyclic β -ketoesters with arylamines is very meagre. Simple and substituted cyclopentan-1-one and cyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylates have been condensed with aniline and other primary aromatic amines both at room and high temperatures^{5,9-15} and some of these reaction products have been cyclised to furnish

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heterocyclic compounds. Thus, Desai and Buksh¹⁶ obtained anils when the above reactions were carried out at low temperature and these on heating alone at 240–250° for 15 min. gave tetrahydroacridones.

Clemo and Mishra¹⁷ condensed ethyl cyclopentan-1-one-2-carboxylate with α -naphthylamine with a view to prepare compounds having a steroid structure with nitrogen as a heteroatom at different positions in the molecule of the azasteroid. It was hoped that these compounds might also possess interesting physiological properties since some basic steroids were earlier synthesised^{18–20} for their biological studies. This ketoester has also been condensed with some heterocyclic amines²¹ with a view to synthesise diaza derivatives of cyclopenta (a) phenanthrene.

The only report about analogous work on seven membered ring system is that of Witkop, Patrick and Rosenblum²² who succeeded in condensing ethyl cycloheptan-1-one-2-carboxylate with aniline and obtained the anilide (II) which on subsequent cyclisation furnished 3:4-cyclohepteno-2-quinolone (III).

Its isomeric product 2:3-cyclohepteno-4-quinolone (IV) was first prepared by Plant and Perkin²³ and later by Witkop *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) by condensing suberone with anthranilic acid. Very recently Bhargava and Saharia (unpublished work) have studied the condensation of ethyl cycloheptan-1-one-2-carboxylate with various arylamines at low and high temperatures and have been able to finally obtain 2:3-cyclohepteno-4-quinolones and 3:4-cyclohepteno-2-quinolones respectively.

Similar condensations of bases with ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-carboxylate have not been reported and it was thought of interest to take up this work with a view to determine the nature of the intermediate products of reaction and the effect of the cyclooctane ring on these condensations and subsequent cyclisations and then to compare the behaviour of these with their lower analogues.

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In the present paper the condensation of ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-carboxylate with aniline, isomeric toluidines, *o*-chloroaniline, *o*- and *m*-anisidines, *o*- and *p*-phenetidines, 2 : 5- and 3 : 4-xylidines at room temperature according to the procedure of Brown *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) is described. The anils (V) so formed were subsequently cyclised by heating at 240–250° to give the corresponding 2 : 3-hexamethylene-aryl substituted-4-quinolones (VI).

β -Naphthylamine, *p*-bromoaniline and *p*-nitraniline failed to react with this β -keto ester.

These reactions proceeded smoothly and the cyclooctane ring hardly offers any resistance during the cyclisations thereby showing that this ring behaves like its lower homologues.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 2 : 3-hexamethylene-Aryl substituted-4-Quinolones. Ethylcyclo-octane-1-one-2-carboxylate : In a three necked R.B. flask equipped with a dropping funnel, a mercury-seal stirrer and a reflux condenser carrying a calcium chloride tube, was placed a solution of sodium ethoxide (sodium, 4.6 g; 0.2 mol) and absolute ethanol (100 ml). The flask was cooled in an ice-salt bath and the stirrer started; when the temperature of the solution had reached 10°, an ice cold mixture of cyclo-octanone (25.2 g; 0.2 mol) and ethyl oxalate (29.2 g; 0.2 mol) was added during 5 mts. After the addition was over, the ice salt bath was retained for 1 hr and the mixture kept stirred at room temperature for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and the solution further diluted; the deposited oil was extracted with benzene (thrice) and the benzene layer dried (Na_2SO_4). After removing the solvent, pure *ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-glyoxalate* distilled at 118–9°/11 mm. (Yield : 23 g; 51.1%) n_D^{21} 1.4768. (Found : C, 63.5; H, 8.00. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 63.7; H, 7.9%). Its alcoholic solution gave a red colouration with aqueous ferric chloride.

To the above ester (23 g.) in a R.B. flask, trace of iron powder and some finely powdered soft glass were added and the contents distilled slowly under reduced pressure; pure *ethylcyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate* had b.p. 101–3°/3 mm; 113–4°/5 mm. (Yield : 20 g; 99.7%) n_D^{21} 1.4758. (Found : C, 66.6; H, 8.9. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.1%).

Its alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with aqueous ferric chloride.

Ethyl-1-arylaminocyclo-oct-1-ene-2-carboxylate : A mixture of ethylcyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate (0.01 mol), the primary aromatic amine (0.01 mol) containing a drop of glacial acetic acid was left over potassium hydroxide in a desiccator under vacuum. The reaction mixture was either distilled in vacuum or crystallised from petrol (40–60°) to give pure *ethyl-1-arylaminocyclo-oct-1-ene-2-carboxylates* (Table I).

TABLE I

Ethyl 1-arylamino-cyclo-oct-1-ene-2-carboxylates

S.No.	Aromatic amine	B.P. or M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Found (%)		Requires (%)	
					C	H	C	H
1.	Aniline	173.4/3 mm	61.5	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	74.3	8.4	74.7	8.4
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	172.4/2.5 mm	50	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₂ N	75.4	8.5	75.2	8.8
3.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	172.3/1.5 mm	61.4	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₂ N	74.9	8.8	75.2	8.8
4.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	67	60.7	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₂ N	75.3	8.6	75.2	8.8
5.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	170.2/2 mm	50	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCl	66.2	7.0	66.3	7.1
6.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	176.7/1.5 mm	61	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₃ N	71.0	8.5	71.2	8.3
7.	<i>m</i> -Anisidine	182.4/2 mm	53	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₃ N	71.1	8.2	71.2	8.3
8.	<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	89	52	C ₁₆ H ₂₇ O ₃ N	71.8	8.6	71.9	8.6
9.	<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	186.8/3 mm	37	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₃ N	71.8	8.4	71.9	8.6
10.	2 : 5-Dimethylaniline	189.90/2 mm	50	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₂ N	75.3	9.0	75.7	9.0
11.	3 : 4-Dimethylaniline	202.4/3 mm	57	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₂ N	75.5	9.2	75.7	9.0

Compounds 4 and 8 were crystallised from petrol ether (40–60°) and benzene-petrol respectively.

2 : 3-Hexamethylene-aryl substituted-4-quinolones : Ethyl-1-arylamino-cyclo-oct-1-ene-2-carboxylate (1 g) was heated in a pyrex tube in a metal bath; the cyclised product was obtained as a solid; on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid the respective 2 : 3-hexamethylene-aryl substituted-4-quinolones were obtained (Table II).

TABLE II

2 : 3-Hexamethylene arylsubstituted-4-quinolones

Sl. No.	Substituent in aromatic ring of the amine	Reaction temp-erature °C	Time hour	Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Found (%)		Requires (%)	
								C	H	C	H
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		
1.	—	240	1	Colourless cubes	Did not melt upto 320	72.3	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON	78.9	7.5	79.3	7.5
2.	8-Methyl	"	"	"	"	74.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	79.4	8.0	79.6	7.9
3.	7-Methyl	"	"	"	"	74.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	79.5	8.0	79.6	7.9
4.	6-Methyl	"	"	"	"	82.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	79.6	7.9	79.6	7.9
5.	8-Chloro	"	"	"	285 (decomp.)	76.6	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ ONCl	68.5	6.3	68.8	6.1
6.	8-Methoxy	"	"	"	Did not melt upto 320	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	74.6	7.6	74.7	7.4
7.	7-Methoxy	"	"	"	"	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	74.6	7.6	74.7	7.4
8.	6-Ethoxy	"	"	"	322	62	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	75.2	7.6	75.2	7.8
9.	8-Ethoxy	"	"	"	296–7	68	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	75.1	8.0	75.2	7.8
10.	5 : 8-Dimethyl	240-250°	½	Chocolate coloured needles.	266	66	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ON	79.8	8.1	80.0	8.2
11.	6 : 7-Dimethyl	"	"	Colourless cubes.	Did not melt upto 320	60	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ON	79.9	8.0	80.0	8.2

All these products were crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

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